

1 **NLRP7 and/or NLRP12 activation as a common route to cellular dysfunction following diverse**
2 **challenges.**

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8 Citations

9 1. Khare, S., Dorfleutner, A., Bryan, N.B., Yun, C., Radian, A.D., de Almeida, L., Rojanasakul, Y. and
10 Stehlik, C., 2012. An NLRP7-containing inflammasome mediates recognition of microbial lipopeptides in
11 human macrophages. *Immunity*, 36(3), pp.464-476.

12 2. Sundaram, B., Pandian, N., Mall, R., Wang, Y., Sarkar, R., Kim, H.J., Malireddi, R.S., Karki, R.,
13 Janke, L.J., Vogel, P. and Kanneganti, T.D., 2023. NLRP12-PANoptosome activates PANoptosis and
14 pathology in response to heme and PAMPs. *Cell*, 186(13), pp.2783-2801.